

Features of the Chilbolton Message.

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ABSTRACT What can the crop circles that appeared near the Chilbolton Observatory in the early 2000’s tell us? What projects might the Chilbolton Message announce? How can we study the process by which crop circles were created?

Tell me, do you... believe in God?
He glanced at me quickly.
— What are you talking about?! Who
believes in... these days?

Stanislav Lem. “Solaris”

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Figure 1 Wiltshire. 13 August 2001.

THE CHILBOLTON MESSAGE.

Crop circles appear all the time, everywhere and in large numbers. Currently, hundreds of drawings are published annually, although the exact number of such objects is unknown. Wikipedia reports that by 2001, more than 10,000 cases of crop circles had been recorded in the former Soviet Union, Great Britain, Japan, the United States and Canada. There are very large images. The figure discovered on August 13, 2001 in Wiltshire had a diameter of about 450 meters and consisted of 409 circles. Incidentally, the famous Stonehenge is located nearby. The media try not to advertise these phenomena too much, since there is not a hint of an explanation of what it is or how such a thing could even occur. Official science does not like to read tea leaves, and crop circles seem to mock its arrogant, pompous self-confidence.

Usually the basis of the drawing is a simple but quite strict geometric construction, reproduced on paper with a compass and ruler. Strictness and simplicity are the main arguments against the natural origin of the phenomenon. Upon detailed examination of the drawings, it turns out that the level of technology required to create the phenomenon significantly exceeds the capabilities of modern civilization. The plants are not “pressed down”, but lose the bearing capacity of the stem through microcracks in the “break” zones. At the same time, the plant never fully ripens, remaining forever green. On the mown field, a kind of ghost of the drawing remains, a “ghost circle”, standing out with its green color on the yellow field

of dried cereals. There are reports that laboratory studies reveal genetic deviations in plants.

Due to the tacit ban on scientific publications about these drawings, it is impossible to provide links to journal articles. However there is extremely important article “Semi-Molten Meteoric Iron Associated with a Crop Formation” written in 1995 by W.C. Levengood and John Burke in the *Journal of Scientific Exploration*, Vol 9, No. 2, pp. 191-199, 1995¹. It is surprising how it could be published? An analogy with ball lightning can be given as an example. No one will doubt that such lightning exists, but there is still no explanation for its stability. Scientific journals are in no hurry to accept articles on this topic, so it is impossible to make, for example, a selection of fresh articles on ball lightning. To explain non-trivial phenomena, non-trivial explanations are needed, but such explanations will be declared “unscientific” at best by the journal, and quackery at worst. At the same time, many popular books describing the field drawings may be found with a simple search on the Internet. It is something between science fiction and descriptions of paranormal phenomena in the style of the American TV series “The X-Files”.

The logic in constructing most of the drawings is trivial and

¹The article may be viewed on the website BLT Research Inc. — [Semi-Molten Meteoric Iron Associated with a Crop Formation](#)

does not go beyond the framework of elementary geometry, but pictures appeared in the fields of Great Britain in 2000-2002 was distinguished by an exceptionally large amount of information and had the character of an “extraterrestrial message”. Detailed descriptions of these drawings have spread widely across the Internet, so any attempt to hide, classify or distort anything is completely excluded. There are no discrepancies or variations in the description of the event, so with a very high probability these messages can be considered quite reliable. Such information can be freely analyzed considering it as source material, regardless of whether it actually happened or not. Proof of the authenticity of the message can be contained in the message itself. A few stanzas on a small piece of paper are enough to establish Pushkin’s hand and a piece of a microcircuit to establish the authorship of Intel.

The interconnected drawings that will be discussed included five images:

- Fractal (August 13, 2000)
- Face (August 14, 2001)
- Message (August 20, 2001)
- Alien (August 15, 2002)
- DNA Ring (August 28, 2002)

Figure 2 Fractal. August 13, 2000.

Figure 3 Face. August 14, 2001.

Since these images are logically connected, one could call them one “Chilbolton message”. This “message” cannot be called strictly “extraterrestrial”, since the basis for the transmission of information was the stalks of cereals planted by quite earthly agricultural workers. And if these drawings were created by some “extraterrestrial intelligence”, then it is obvious that this intelligence is not so far from our Earth or has direct access to it. In addition, this “EI” has gone very far in its development.

First of all, it is necessary to note the features of the “Face” image. If an ordinary drawing on a field is a binary image, where the areas of broken and standing stalks are presented as zeros and ones, then the “Face” is made using a much more advanced technology. An unknown artist tried to illustrate the transmission of an analog signal. At first glance, viewed from almost any direction and at any angle, the picture represented something indefinite and shapeless. The “Face” of a person appeared only from a certain point in the air above the Earth, and only under a certain direction of solar illumination, that is, only at certain hours. This effect was achieved in the following way:

In the “Face” image, the plant stems, as usual, had no visible damage and were bent at various angles, and the stems were not broken, but had lost their load-bearing capacity due to microscopic holes at the bending point. Moreover, the arrangement of plants was done in several layers, each of which was twisted in the opposite direction from the previous one. Paul Vigey, a researcher who visited and studied this image, said that “Each individual circle appeared to be twisted

Figure 4 Message. August 20, 2001.

separately from the rest of the formation, as indicated by the smooth curl of the plants around each circle.”

The overall appearance of the image imitated a picture in a book, newspaper or magazine – it was a “pixelated” image with halftones. The dots were of different sizes, which created the impression of depth. The “Face” looked as if it was drawn on a crumpled piece of paper. The placement of the image, however, was tied to the geometry of the real field: the imprint of the tractor wheels crossed the “Face” exactly in the middle, dividing it in half.

“The Face” appeared the day after the giant drawing appeared in Wiltshire.

Figure 5 Alien. August 15, 2002.

Figure 6 DNA Ring. August 28, 2002.

The “Message” was a broadside recreation of a digital message that was transmitted in 1974 by the Arecibo radio telescope toward the globular cluster M13, with some significant modifications. This material is well known.

Silicon has been added to the list of chemical elements that make up Earth’s DNA.

On the right side of the “Message” is a DNA strand with a geometry different from the standard. Earth DNA contains 10 base pairs per turn. The “Message” depicted a strand with 6 base pairs per turn.

The man in the Arecibo message was above one raised dot, corresponding to the planet Earth. In the “Message”, a being with a large head and a small body was above three raised dots, with the leftmost one being a small diamond made up

of four dots.

Instead of a schematic image of a radio telescope in the Arecibo message, the field showed a geometric picture consisting of many circles of different sizes.

The “Fractal” image that appeared in front of the Chilbolton Radio Telescope on August 13, 2000, was a more detailed image of the geometric pattern at the bottom of “The Message”.

The “DNA Ring” image that appeared on August 28, 2002 was a DNA helix with 6 base pairs per turn, as on the left side of the “Message”.

Figure 7 Messages comparison.

The “Alien” that appeared on August 15, 2002, the stereotype of the “Grey Extraterrestrial” from modern science fiction films, corresponded in the “Message” to a little man with a big head.

The dates of the appearance of the “Face” 08/14/2001 and the “Message” 08/20/2001 together give 1420 MHz – the radio line of neutral hydrogen, and the year 2001 → 21 its wavelength. Other interesting parallels are possible.

This article makes assumptions about what the unknown artist wanted to tell humanity and what this artist himself might represent.

Figure 8 Some parallels in the drawings.

DID GOD HAVE A CHOICE IN CREATING OUR WORLD?

This question is said to belong to Albert Einstein. In other words, could our world have been built differently, according to other principles, or is everything strictly unambiguous? The author of the Chilbolton Message, apparently, in particular, answers this question.

Silicon may have been used in constructing the DNA structure.

No DNA or proteins used in biological structures found on Earth include silicon. The descriptions of DNA nucleotides in the Arecibo text and the “Message” are identical and also do not include silicon. However, the essential fact is the fundamental possibility of using silicon instead of phosphorus in the “skeleton” of DNA, to which the nucleotide bases are attached. Then PO_4 is replaced there by SiO_4 – a well-known and widespread silicate.

It can be assumed that the DNA structure where SiO_4 is used instead of PO_4 has other physical properties, can be much stronger and more rigid, which significantly changes the processes of replication and transcription. It is possible that DNA with a silicon backbone will have 6 pairs per turn instead of 10 – as it is presented in the “Message” and the

Figure 9 The structure of Earth's DNA.

picture “DNA Ring”. The choice of PO_4 for the construction of the Earth's DNA was probably related to the adequacy of structural properties for optimizing genetic transformations. At the same time, it is possible that DNA with a backbone including silicon can be used as a kind of supplement in solving, say, the problem of improving the human immune system, similar to how silicone prostheses are used to eliminate skeletal defects. I considered the hypothesis of the possibility of the existence of such a silicon virus in the articles “The HIV++ Immune Upgrade Virus. Hypothesis of existence.”² and “Hypothesis of existence of symbiosis between the immune upgrade virus HIV++ and the coronavirus SARS-CoV-2”³.

Habitable zone, Phaeton and the Titius-Bode rule.

In the Arecibo message, the Solar System consists of nine planets. The human is above the slightly raised third planet. This indicates that humans live on the third planet. In the “Message”, three planets are raised, and the outermost one is drawn as a diamond. It can be assumed that this is how the “Message” presented the “habitable zone” of the Solar System, and this zone should also include a certain fifth planet. In both the Arecibo message and the “Message”, Jupiter and Saturn are indicated by longer segments.

It is known that there is a Titius-Bode rule, which is an empirical formula that depends on the distance of a planet from the Sun and its ordinal number. According to this rule, there should have been another planet between Mars and Jupiter. There have been suggestions that such a planet, called “Phaeton” or Olbers’ planet, actually existed before, but then disintegrated or exploded, turning into the asteroid

²Article on zenodo.org – Immune upgrade virus HIV++. Hypothesis of existence.

³Article on figshare.com – Hypothesis of existence of symbiosis between the immune upgrade virus HIV++ and the coronavirus SARS-CoV-2

belt. Modern science does not support this point of view, since the total mass of all the asteroids in the belt is only 4% of the mass of the Moon. However, there is a possibility that most of Phaeton simply dispersed into space as dust after the cataclysm, and this could have happened at the stage of the formation of the Solar System and was not a consequence of a thermonuclear war of the inhabitants of Phaeton. The unknown artist may have wanted to say that life could have arisen or been created in the Solar System not only on Earth, there were options. Earth simply represented the best option of all possible.

Figure 10 Titius-Bode rule.

Figure 11 Patomskiy crater.

The existence of the Titius-Bode rule may indicate that the entire Solar System arose as a result of some central process in which the wave properties of matter manifested themselves. There are no theories of such a way of the origin of the Solar System today. Since stars are the most common type of existence of matter in the Universe, there must be some single mechanism for their origin. In the article “How to find and study the “body” of the Tunguska event.”⁴ I made an assumption that the Tunguska explosion is essentially identical to

⁴Article on zenodo.org – How to find and study the “body” of the Tunguska event.

any earthquake, as well as the process of the origin of all stellar systems. A certain soliton-like object of a wave nature, that is, matter with an integer spin, under certain circumstances, possibly somehow related to gravity, is capable of transforming into matter with a half-integer spin. In this case, ordinary particles with mass arise, forming all the elements of the periodic table. Based on energy considerations, the formation of an iron-nickel mixture similar to the substance of meteorites is more likely. The original soliton-like object has no mass, does not interact gravitationally and interacts very weakly electromagnetically. The result of the passage of such an object through the surface of the Earth may have been the famous “Patomskiy crater”.

A SCIENTIFIC METHOD FOR STUDYING CROP CIRCLES.

When analyzing the “Message,” one can notice that the diamond of the fifth planet is identical to the diamond in the center of the image that replaced the image of the radio telescope in the original Arecibo message. This may indicate that the process that destroyed the planet Phaeton, unknown to modern science, is also used to create crop circles (the image is presented instead of the radio telescope). A very specific method for studying these drawings may be associated with this assumption.

Any scientific method of research requires the ability to conduct an experiment that does not depend on random circumstances – which can be repeated by anyone, anywhere, at any time. This is precisely what the “unscientific” nature of ball lightning is associated with. Until now, no one has been able to create this phenomenon in a laboratory setting, since even the principles of how it can be created are still unknown. No one has yet succeeded in directly studying natural ball lightning, since its appearance is completely unpredictable. In this regard, the situation with crop circles is much better - there are more than enough objects for study and any researcher can regularly access them: crop circles appear all over the world.

Figure 12 Acceleration of tree growth in the Tunguska region.

Figure 13 Green ghost on a mown field.

The article “Semi-Molten Meteoric Iron Associated with a Crop Formation” provides extremely important information about the formation of iron particles identical in composition to meteorites on the area of the pattern. It cannot be said that science completely ignored this message. Several experiments were conducted at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology to study these iron particles. Some results of these studies can be found on the website [BLT Research Team Inc.](#) It is clear though that the funds that finance scientific research are unlikely to actively support the study of any dubious phenomena.

If we assume that the “Fractal” picture, corresponding to what replaced the Arecibo radio telescope in the “Message”, somehow describes the process that simultaneously underlies the formation of the Solar System and the crop patterns, then the method for studying the crop patterns should be identical to the method for studying the Tunguska explosion. Studying the soil composition features in the area of any such pattern can help answer the question of how star systems arise in the Universe.

In addition to iron particles, the composition of which repeats that of meteorites, it is necessary to examine the soil for elements from the entire periodic table. It is known that a slightly elevated radiation background is observed at the place where the pattern appears. This may be due to short-lived radioactive elements, the presence of which is especially easy to determine. This causes genetic abnormalities in plants.

The size of soliton-like quasi particles, which serve as embryos of such processes, can, apparently, be completely arbitrary. If the stems of cereals bend as a result of the transition of mass-less solitons into matter with mass and at the same time it is possible to draw a pattern with a sufficiently high resolution, then the size of the quasi particles can be not only stellar in scale, but also comparable to the thickness of the stems of cereals, or even smaller and uniformly fill the entire space of the field. The pattern is formed by external action on the quasi particles, which causes their disintegration into a mass object.

One of the hypotheses for the origin of such particles in the Earth is the decay or disintegration of protons, which results in the formation of a free electron and a soliton-like wave

object. The imbalance of electrons causes the Earth to have a charge. The excess of free electrons interacting with the Earth's magnetic field causes typhoons, and the soliton-like mass-less remnants of protons with an integer spin can stick together and cause earthquakes, turning back into a mass form.

Completely independent of how the process of transition of matter from a state with an integer spin to a state with a half-integer spin occurs, with the help of crop circles this process can be studied using a fine correlation-statistical analysis of the composition of the soil over the entire area of the drawing on the field. Not only particles of meteorite composition should be found there, but any element of Mendeleev table and the anomalies in the composition of the soil will change over time. The fresh mass that results from the process in question apparently serves as a strong fertilizer for plants, stimulating growth, so the broken stalks of cereals do not wither and leave green pictures on the field, "ghost images" against the background of a yellowed field. This probably occurs similarly to the abnormally rapid growth of trees in the Tunguska explosion area.

ANTHROPOLOGY OF GOD. HUMANITARIAN PROJECT.

If DNA with non-traditional geometry and the addition of silicon can relate to medicine and genetics, and experiments with processes unknown to science relate to physics and astrophysics, then the drawings "Face" and "Alien" can announce a purely humanitarian project. What the essence of this project is can only be guessed at.

The question of the existence of "God" has always been a very complex and ambiguous topic. There are no two religions in which "God" would be understood as the same thing. The question "Do you believe in God?" makes sense only within the framework of one religion. A more correct question would be "Which God do you believe in?" Although if you ask this question to a Buddhist, he may ask for a definition of "God" – in Buddhism this concept is absent. Siddhartha Gautama did not like the hundreds of thousands of Hindu gods very much. In the famous film "Chariots of the Gods", "Gods" are associated with "Extraterrestrial Intelligence".

If "God" exists, he may have great difficulty in proving his own existence. If he does not play into the existing stereotypes, any appearance of him may be regarded as a hoax. In order to "return to mankind" "God" must not only paint a detailed portrait of himself, but also prove its authenticity. Montaigne wrote very well on this topic in the preface to his "Essays":

...I want to be seen in my simple, natural and ordinary appearance, unconstrained and unartificial, for I am not painting anyone but myself. My faults will appear here as living, and my whole appearance as it really is, as far as, of course, this is compatible with my respect for the public...

...the content of my book is myself, and this is by no means a reason for you to devote your leisure to such a frivolous and insignificant subject.

It is the theme of self-portrait that comes to mind when considering the image of the "Face" in the Chilbolton message. Analogue images are distinguished by the ability to convey an infinite number of halftones, and the book technique of the "Face" says that this "Face" is drawn in books. A person can understand only based on his own experience and the possibilities available to him. Explaining to a dog what he is, a human must imagine himself as a dog, based on the rules and laws by which dogs live, using dog language. Therefore, any image of "God" that is accessible to understanding can only be anthropogenic, that is, made in the image and likeness of a human. For a complete reflection, it must obviously use the properties of many people at once and the abilities of a wide variety of writers. Perhaps this is what the giant painting in Wiltshire says?

In the article "Principles of Scientific Religion."⁵ I made an assumption about the existence of a certain global project, including the work of writers and poets from many countries over the past millennium, whose main role is to draw a portrait of "my beloved self", to try to explain what the "Extraterrestrial Intelligence" called "God" is, what problems it worries about and what useful things people can take from this for themselves. At the same time, all these writers unconsciously play the role of prophets, that is, they write down what is dictated to them from above under hypnosis. There is nothing new – this is how the concept of a prophet is interpreted in the Abrahamic religions, where it arose.

Figure 14 Russian literature and the Renaissance.

In contrast to the "Face" which represents a real person in an analog version, i.e. which assumes an infinite number of halftones, the "Alien" drawing is a simple stereotype of the "Grey Extraterrestrial" image taken from films like "The X-Files". Along with the alien there is a disk with several phrases recorded on it in digital form in ASCII encoding in English.

Beware the bearers of FALSE gifts & their BROKEN PROMISES. Much PAIN but still time. EEL-

⁵Article on zenodo.org [Principles of Scientific Religion](#).

RIJUE. There is GOOD out there. We OPpose
DECEPTION. Conduit CLOSING [bell sound]

The author of the image transmits a signal, as if in the amplitude modulation of radio receivers, which is interrupted by noise (EELRIJUE). The recording on the disk corresponds to the technology that was most widespread in the early 2000's – as is done on CD and DVD disks. Messages from extraterrestrial civilizations are traditionally tried to catch on the analog frequencies of the hydrogen line – 1420 MHz, which corresponds to the dates of the appearance of the “Face” and the “Message” – 14 and 20 respectively.

The phrase “BROKEN PROMISES” refers to the composition “Sorrow” by Pink Floyd. Losing faith is always very unpleasant.

A man lies and dreams of green fields and rivers
But awakes to a morning with no reason for waking
He's haunted by the memory of a lost paradise
In his youth or a dream, he can't be precise
He's chained forever to a world that's departed

And silence that speaks so much louder, than words
Of promises broken.

Why did the “Extraterrestrial Intelligence”, which is called “God”, leave all its prophecies thousands of years ago and then fall silent? Perhaps the message he wrote for a thousand years contains the answer to this question.

The phrase “out there” refers to the main slogan of the series “The X-Files” – “The truth is out there”. The central theme of the series is the existence of an alien virus that can cure many diseases such as cancer. A destructive creature, the virus directs its capabilities to destroying man's enemies. This can cause accompanying negative side effects – hence “Much PAIN but still time”.

The last composition of the Pink Floyd album “The Division Bell” – “High Hopes” ends with the ringing of a bell. The title of the album “The Division Bell” refers to the bell that hung in the House of Commons of the British Parliament and with its ringing warned of the upcoming vote. The main theme of the album is the loss of understanding, the emergence of contradictions, connections between people. In the Chilbolton Message, the bell rings after the communication channel, conduit is closed.

The front cover of the album “The Division Bell” depicts two strange figures who seem to be talking to each other, and on the line of this dialogue, there are red flags, in another version bright lights. The two figures looking at each other merge into one, which looks forward at the viewer. In the distance, if you jump behind the flags, the silhouette of the Cathedral of the Holy and *Undivided* Trinity in the city of Ely, Cambridgeshire, England appears. The image of these metal statues was created under the influence of the Aku-Aku statues from Easter Island. The “face” in the Chilbolton message is divided exactly in half by the tracks of the tractor and the oval of the face is slightly reminiscent of the figure on the cover of the album “The Division Bell”.

Figure 15 The Division Bell. Pink Floyd.

Figure 16 Aku-aku on Easter Island.

It can be assumed that for an adequate understanding of the self-portrait of “Extraterrestrial Intelligence”, the highest level of abstraction is required. Such a self-portrait does not necessarily have to be simple and understandable “on the hailstones”, for a wide range of people. The author is in no hurry and does not at all need to write something that should please someone or that can be used for utilitarian needs.

Like an eagle, he flies
 And, without asking anyone,
 As Desdemona chooses
 An idol for her heart.⁶

The style of the “essay” in the spirit of Montaigne’s books fully satisfies these requirements. The author writes about himself and is not very concerned with the opinion of the crowd, which is quite consonant with the main epigraph to Pushkin’s poem “Eugene Onegin”:

Petri de vanite il avait encore plus de cette espece
 d’orgueil qui fait avouer avec la meme indifference
 les bonnes comme les mauvaises actions, suite d’un
 sentiment de superiorite peut-etre imaginaire. Tire
 d’une lettre particuliere.

Filled with vanity, he also possessed a special pride which makes one confess with equal indifference both one’s good and bad deeds – a consequence of a feeling of superiority, perhaps imaginary. From a private letter.

⁶A.S. Pushkin. “Egyptian Nights”